

Failure logistic regression: Firth-corrected vs unpenalized
transmitted ~ observability + institutional_flag + time_depth_z (n=26)

- Firth-corrected (PL 95% CI)
- Unpenalized Wald (clipped at ± 15)

Observability
(continuous, 0-1)

Institutional flag
(binary)

Time depth
(z-scored years BP)

